

Purification of further GS loop mutants of ALK2 (ACVR1) to investigate necessary phosphorylation's for SMAD1 activation.

Proteins to be purified:

ACVR1Z-c105

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHACASGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETelyNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSlyDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNL
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDsYKRVDIWAfGLVlWEVARRMVSNGIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSdPTLTLsLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKkTLTKID

ACVR1Z-c106

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHsCTAGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETelyNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSlyDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNL
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDsYKRVDIWAfGLVlWEVARRMVSNGIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSdPTLTLsLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKkTLTKID

ACVR1Z-c109

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHsCTAGAGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETelyNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSlyDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNL
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDsYKRVDIWAfGLVlWEVARRMVSNGIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSdPTLTLsLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKkTLTKID

*/ Indicates tev cleavage site.

Expression:

Cells were expressed in Sf9 insect cells using baculo infection system. Cells were transfected and after 96h harvested at 900g for 20 minutes before freezing at -20 prior to purification.

Purification:

For all samples

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate all other samples for 3 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice for baculo cells.
- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (aprox 40ml per tube).

- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21.5k rpm for 50 minutes.
- Incubate lysate with 2.5ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.

Figure 1: SDS-PAGE gel of Nickle purification of ACVR1Z-c105 and c106 showing flow through, washes 1 and 2 and four elution fractions. The red box indicates samples taken on for additional purification. The Orange box indicated unbound c106 requiring further purification and the green box shows gel band sent for MS/MS identification – result shows this band is not ACVR1.

ACVR1Z c109 Ni col (1)

and Ni col (2)

Figure 2: left SDS-PAGE gel of Nickel purification of ACVR1Z-c109 showing flow through, washes 1 and 2 and four elution fractions with protein mostly in the FT and W1. The red box indicates samples taken on for additional purification. Right, the results of re-probing the FT and the Wash with additional 5ml of Ni resin and subsequent recovery of protein. The boxed samples were taken for purification with a GF75 column.

For ACVR1Z-c106 only

- Re-Incubate lysate with 5ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.
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Figure 3: SDS-PAGE of rescued ACVR1A-c106 re-incubation with Ni NTA resin, with 1 wash with wash buffer and 3 x E4 washes.

For ACVR1Z-c109 only:

- Re-Incubate lysate with 5ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.
- Add Tev protease to fractions which contain protein

All samples

- Concentrate down relevant fractions to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 75 column for all samples using standard gel filtration buffer (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 0.5mM TCEP, pH7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of peak.

ACVR1Z c105

Figure 4: SDS-PAGE gel of ACVR1Z c105 gel filtration samples (top) and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs (bottom) using a GF75 size exclusion column. Sample was split into 2 aliquots of <5ml each and run in two batches to prevent overloading the column.

ACVR1Z c106

Figure 5: SDS-PAGE gel of ACVR1Z c106 gel filtration samples (left) and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs (right) using a GF75 size exclusion column.

ACVR1Z-c109 – GF75

Figure 6: SDS-PAGE gel of ACVR1Z-c109 gel filtration samples (left) and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs (right) using a GF75 size exclusion column.

ACVR1Z-c106 ONLY

Tev cleavage was incomplete so more Tev was added overnight at 4C and then a Nickle rebind was done to remove un-cleaved sample.

- Incubate with 2ml of pre-equilibrated Ni NTA beads for 1h at 4C
- Wash with 20ml Wash buffer
- Elute in 1x7ml E4 buffer.
- All fractions show cleaved protein (Tev must have worked overnight with added exposure) so pool all fractions for future use.

Figure 7: SDS PAGE gel of nickel rebind of ACVR1-c106.

All Samples:

Concentrate down purified fractions until high enough concentration (>200uM if possible) in the presence of 10mM DTT. Aliquot out and flash freeze in liquid nitrogen for storage at -80C.